

Implementation by inclusivity in European health system-level digital solutions

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Abstract

User inclusion in digital development is fundamental to fostering transparency, equity, and trust in healthcare systems. It plays a crucial role in ensuring that digital health solutions are both high-quality and capable of achieving widespread implementation. This article examines the role of inclusivity in European health system-level digital solutions, with a particular focus on access to clinical studies, system-level health data, and accessibility platforms for personal health data management. By addressing these key areas, we highlight the transformative potential of participatory approaches for a more inclusive and sustainable digital health landscape.

Background

This article analyses lessons learned from several European projects concerning the role of health literacy towards inclusivity in European health

system-level digital solutions. Research has shown that low health literacy levels correlate with reduced participation in medical research, poorer health outcomes, and increased healthcare inequalities (1–3). Digital platforms must prioritise clear, user-friendly communication strategies that enhance understanding and empower individuals to make informed decisions, such as plain language, multimedia formats, and culturally adapted materials that accommodate diverse linguistic and cognitive needs (4).

Ethical dimensions of inclusive digital health cannot be overlooked. Transparency in data collection, privacy protections, and equitable access to digital resources are critical to ensuring trust in digital health initiatives. Ethical frameworks, such as those outlined in the General Data Protection Regulation (GDPR) and the European Medicines Agency (EMA) guidelines, provide essential safeguards but must be implemented alongside participatory approaches (5) that involve patients, researchers, and policymakers in decision-making processes and proactive measures to prevent biases.

Methods

Using a thematic analysis, we have examined outputs from projects such as AAL GotIT (6), COST Action NET4Age-Friendly (7), IHI READI (8), and Horizon Europe's RadioVal (9). All these initiatives highlight best practices in digital inclusion, based on the positive benefit to user uptake and willingness to use digital tools, demonstrating how strategic frameworks can be implemented to create more accessible and ethical clinical studies. In addition, the analysis integrated key methods foundational to value-driven movements such as Nordic Health 2030 (10), the SHAFE Foundation (11), and the International Health Literacy Association (12) on fostering a patient-centred, inclusive research environments.

Results

Findings are clear: inclusivity is a core element for both speed and quality in digital development. Reducing inclusion might reduce time for short-term development processes, but at the expense of overall slower uptake

or impact (AAL GotIT and NET4Age Friendly). The full cycle of digital implementation needs to be considered as a fundamental part of the uptake process, to which inclusivity is a critical enabler.

Inclusion of diverse user groups promotes transparency, equity, and trust in digital health, exemplified by two key areas for implementation of future health technology: clinical studies and uptake of artificial intelligence (RadioVal and IHI READI).

The analysis also found that digital health literacy has a significant divergence from the overall health literacy of included users. The ability to navigate, interact, or integrate digital solutions requires a different subset of skills, adding to the many challenges of traditional health literacy. In part, this is also because contrary to traditional information or communication tools, that are in nature mono-directional, the digital tools are often used for dual purposes – creating potential pathways for communication back and forth between professionals, patients, and caregivers, but also across professionals and users (13).

Digital health technologies can act as facilitators for greater inclusivity in clinical studies, improving access, enhancing health literacy, and addressing ethical considerations. In many cases, underserved or marginalised populations, such as older adults, people with lower socioeconomic status, ethnic minorities, and individuals with limited digital literacy, face significant barriers to participation in clinical research, exacerbated by complex trial protocols, limited awareness, and digital divides (e.g. online platforms, e-consent procedures). Addressing these challenges requires the integration of inclusive design principles (4), ensuring that digital tools are not only accessible but also clear to a diverse range of users (14).

For AI uptake, inclusivity plays two vital roles: in diagnostics and in secondary use of health data for prevention. For the uptake of AI diagnostic tools in clinical practice or in primary care settings, inclusivity is essential for trust and transparency, e.g., by using low-tech co-design workshops, user

journey mapping, or iterative user feedback loops. These add quality to the development process (15), reduce expensive redesign, and gather potential ambassadors and early adopters. In the secondary use of health data for prevention, inclusivity in development and oversight is key to reducing system bias (16) that would otherwise both skew results and reduce the uptake of AI-powered analysis or suggestions.

In both cases, AI can be used to find data patterns and trends that traditional methods would miss or not be able to conclude. However, given the current state of health services, healthcare professionals and/or patients would initially risk seeing these results as counterintuitive to the traditional method and consider the analysis flawed or biased. From Semmelweis to Jon Snow, the introduction of new analysis counter to existing practice tends to struggle for uptake. Inclusivity in the development and deployment process is an antidote to this.

Conclusions

The future of digital uptake in Europe must be shaped by inclusive digital development strategies. In clinical studies, they can actively dismantle barriers to participation, enhance health literacy by boosting empowerment and agency, and uphold ethical standards. By integrating patient voices into the design process, leveraging innovative digital tools, and ensuring equitable access, clinical research can become more representative, ethical, and impactful, contributing to a more just and transparent medical research landscape.

In the implementation of upcoming AI tools for diagnostics and public health, inclusivity by integration of user perspectives and insights in both strategy and implementation is essential to enable trust (17). And subsequently to the speed of uptake of new clinical and community practices that can actively contribute to better wellbeing for people and professionals by improved prevention, reduction of workloads, personalised solutions, and higher quality of care.

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